

Grandma's Ho's Digital Marketing Strategy in Improving Brand Awareness Through Instagram Social Media

(Grandma's House Bintaro Case Study, Southjakarta)

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Abstract:- Grandma's House coffee shop or coffeshop is one form of MSMEs that was established in 2020 in Bintaro area, South Jakarta. Along with the development of this business and spearheaded by the parties in it is expected to be able to compete with other coffee shops with the strategy owned. This research presents digital marketing in increasing brand awareness through Insatgram social media as an effort to inform, and remind consumers about Grandma's House as one of the MSMEs products that sell various variants of coffee flavors with special signatures presented. The selection of social media and the selection of strategies used by Grandma's House to increase brand awareness became the goal of the research. This research is conducted with qualitative research methods. Data the studies obtained also come from all parties concerned, both throughinterviews, and documentation. Informant consists of three main informants namely Owner, Head Marketing, and Social Media Team. The results showed that digital marketing strategies in increasing brand awareness were carried out using Instagram social media by affirming the slogan "As comfortable as grandma's house" and doing activities in the form of product promotion through posts with interesting captions in an effort to increase brand awareness about coffee products presented by Grandma's House.

Keywords:- Brand Awareness, Digital Marketing, Instagram.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of information technology, especially the internet, has changed the way humans communicate. The presence of the internet in human life provides convenience for people to access the information needed. This is because the internet becomes the main source of information that has a high level of interaction and customization so that it can provide an experience according to the needs of its users. In the modern era as in this day and age, humans are able to do various activities in the house or in the office without having to plunge directly with other vehicles andheat onthe road. With internet technology, humans can do many things such as socializing, greeting friends far and near, reading books,

obtaining various information, even shopping online. This also encourages thedevelopment of technology, such as promotional facilities to increase through the use of Internet media. With this medium, the company does not require much to promote the product, in addition to its vast reach.

The Internet is very useful in various fields, especially for MSMEs in running their business. The Financial Services Authority noted that the distribution of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) continues to grow towards the end of 2020. Credit has the potential to grow along with the high need for new capital in 2021. Now s recorded more than 65 million MSMEs spread in Indonesia. In 2016, there were 61.7 million MSMEs in Indonesia. The number continues to increase, in 2017, the number of MSMEs reached 62.9 million and in 2018, the number of MSMEs reached 64.2 million. It is predicted that in 2019, 2020 to 2021 the number continues to increase.

Fig 1: The amount of MSME data in Indonesia according to Tempo.co

Digital marketing is the use of the Internet as a technology that can connect two-way communication between companies and consumers (Coviello, 2001). *Digital marketing facilitates* sales promotion, such as the use of social media that is widely used by marketers. As a discipline that combines the art of management with computers, making digital marketing quite in demand by manypeople. According to ideoworks.com, MSMEs can take a big part in the market if they have the right marketing team, including using digital marketing or digital *marketing* as a strategy to attract buyers. It is also supported by data showing that 87%

of shoppers will search for products online (according to *RetailDive*). Interestingly, the number of Digital Agency Indonesia is now increasing. So that MSME owners will not have difficulty in marketing products digitally. Not only that's the reason MSMEs need to use *digital marketing*. Digital marketing can reach all circles, anytime, in any way, and anywhere. Of course, it is far superior to conventional marketing that is limited in time, location, and userreach.

One of the MSME business people who utilize digital marketing itself is Grandma's House. As one of *Coffeshop* or coffee shop located in Bintaro, which has the slogan "As comfortable as grandma's house" is utilizing Digital Marketing to increase brand *awareness* in the midst of intense coffee shop competition that is quite significantly increased, especially in bintaro area, South Jakarta. Grandma's House certainly applies digital marketing as one of the process of introducing its products to young people and the surrounding community as well as to advance MSME business in Indonesia.

Technological advances, especially the field of information gave birth to new concepts to the field of marketing. Many companies inform and promote their products only directly in stores, but can now utilize technology as a means of promotion. However, internet companies can market their products quickly with wide reach, as well as Grandma's House in promoting coffee products sold. In building awareness of the Grandma's House brand or brand, of course, the owner of the coffee shop chooses social media to do marketing activities, in hopes of competing with other coffee shops and also become a coffee shop that is always remembered and can be known by the general public. Promotional activities through social media are expected to be the main factor in increasing and maintaining brand *awareness*, where consumers are more aware and remember the products produced so as to ultimately make consumers become loyal to the product.

Brand awareness as a marketing strategy becomes the most important factor in building consumer awareness to buy a product. Through consumer awareness of a brand, prospective consumers can remember and know the brand and decide to make a purchase, allowing consumers to only make purchases to one particular brand category. The term strategy is often used by the public to describe something like some goal to be achieved. Just like Grandma's House in doing a strategy to achieve the goal.

Instagram is the main social media that Grandma's House uses to promote its products. The application that is current and most widely used by the wider community is one of the media that focus on one's activities to disseminate to the wider community and promote a product so that the public can know the activities of a person or company that he does. Instagram is a photo sharing application that allows users to take short photos and videos, apply digital filters, and then share them to various social media including Instagram itself. The development also switched functions from initially just sharing photos or videos uploaded into promotional containers. With the advantages of social media, Grandma's

House uses Instagram social media as a digital *marketing* medium in promoting it.

In this study, digital marketing in increasing Grandma's House *brand awareness* was done through social media, not only the products that were the focus but also consumers. Through social media, a brand can interact with consumers and potential customers directly. In social media can also be seen the response and reaction of consumers to the product so that it can adjust the promotional strategy to be used. In its management must also have the right strategy. Social media account managers should be active and often post about products offered to consumers and keep interacting with *followers*. Another important thing in managing social media is what content will be created to attract consumers to get attention and interact through social media that we use to promote products.

Sostac planning model became a foundation in this research, which is one of the models of digital marketing planning to be more effective in the application of digital marketing in a company to market its products. Sostac was developed by Paul R. Smith in 1990, following the sostac stages consisting of analysis of situations, objectives, strategies, tactics, actions, and controls that are the basis in identifying marketing problems in the company so as to produce the best and effective planning model. This research focuses on Grandma's House's digital marketing strategy that utilizes Instagram as a promotional medium, Instagram account @grandamhousee as a means of promotional media ranging from display every homemade coffee product then generated from some previous consumers. In this case, the researchers put a limit that the research is the promotion of goods sold using the SOSTAC method. From the description above, this article focuses on *digital marketing* activities in increasing Grandma's House brand *awareness*.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The research methods used in this research are qualitative with case studies as a research approach. The basis of qualitative research is to form a view of the informants in detail, which is outlined through words thoroughly. Data studies obtained also come from all parties concerned, either through interviews, or documentation.

The object in this study is *digital marketing* in increasing brand *awareness*, while the subject of the study is *Coffeshop* Grandma's House. To get data validation, in this study researchers used triangulation of data that is obtained from various sources obtained by various data collection techniques (triangulation), and continuously until the data is saturated in the form of interviews, documentation, and some records contained in the field.

The interview is conducted after going through the observation process so that the data obtained is in accordance with the results of observations about the research subject. The interview was conducted to Grandma's House's Marketing Team which includes *the Owner, Head Marketing, and Social Media Team*. Some selected informants are randomly determined and based on the criteria required as a

research source. The research site was conducted at Grandma's House Jl. RC Veteran 20, Bintaro, South Jakarta.

III. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

➤ *Digital Marketing*

Quoting the opinion of Ridwan Sanjaya and Josua Tarigan (2009) *digital marketing* is a marketing activity including *branding* that uses various web-based media such as email, adwords, or other social networking media, which needs to be underlined is digital marketing not just talking to internet marketing. According to Kotler (2012, in Oktaviani and Rustani, 2018), digital marketing is used by marketers because with the easy use of social media, the process also facilitates sales promotion. Companies use social media as a means for consumers to disseminate information in the form of text, images, audio, and video with many parties either between companies to consumers or consumers in the company (Kotler, 2012).

➤ *Marketing Communications*

Marketing communication is a means of marketing in which a company seeks to inform, inform and remind consumers, either directly or indirectly about a product they are selling. Marketing communication is also useful as a medium of knowledge for consumers, also showing consumers how or why a product is used, and where and whenever.

According to Kennedy and Soemanagara (2006) marketing communication is a marketing activity using communication techniques that aim to provide information to the audience so that the company's goals are achieved, and increasing revenue is a major goal of this.

➤ *Brand Awareness*

According to Durianto (2004: 54), *brand awareness* is the ability of a prospective buyer to recognize and recall a brand as part of a product category. In this case, of course, it can include certain names, images, logos, and slogans used by marketers to promote their products. It can be said, brand awareness becomes one of the important factors needed by business people to strengthen their product brand. Because if more consumers remember the brand of a product, then the greater the intensity of purchases they will make.

Some stages in brand awareness, namely first, *unaware of a brand* or not recognizing a brand is the lowest level in the brand awareness pyramid. At this level the user is not aware of and unaware of the existence of a brand or brand in a particular category. Second, *brand recognition* is a minimal level of brand awareness. Brand recognition includes the ability of consumers or users to recognize a brand with tools. Third, *brand recall* or recall. Brand awareness immediately appears in the minds of consumers after a particular brand is mentioned. Unlike recognition that requires tools, brand recall only requires repetition or re-mention of similar brands to remember the brand of the product. And fourth, *top of mind* or peak. This level is the highest level where a particular brand has dominated the minds of consumers. The brand will appear in the minds of consumers when the product category is given.

➤ *SOSTAC model*

SOSTAC is one of the models of digital marketing planning to be more effective in the application of digital marketing in a company to market its products. Sostac itself was originally developed by Paul R. Smith in 1990, the following stages of SOSTAC consisting of analysis of situations, objectives, strategies, tactics, actions, and controls that are the basis in identifying the problems of a marketing in the company so as to produce the best and effective planning model, including:

1. *Situation Analysis*. In this early stage, the situation analysis used is SWOT analysis. SWOT analysis is the systematic identification of 24 factors to formulate a company's strategy. This analysis is suggested on logic that can maximize Strengths and Opportunities, but strategically always related to the development of the company's mission, goals, strategies, and policies. Thus strategic planner must analyze the factors of the company's strategy (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) and the current conditions.

2. *Objectives*. Goals in digital marketing include aspects of task, quantity and time. Tasks (what will be achieved), measurable quantity (by how much) and Time frame (when). Most digital marketing aims to: increase market share, increase the number of comments on a blog or website, increase sales revenue, reduce costs (distribution or promotional costs), achieve brand goals (increase brand awareness), increase database size, achieve Customer Relationship Management (CRM) goals (increase customer satisfaction, purchase frequency, or customer reference rate), improve supply chain management (increasing brand awareness). member coordination, adding partners, or optimizing inventory levels).

3. *Strategic Planning (Planning Strategy)*. *Digital marketing* is at the core of an e-business, with a company getting closer to customers and understanding it better, adding value to a product, expanding its distribution network, and also increasing sales numbers.

4. *Tactics/Implementation Plan*. At this stage the company decides how to achieve its goals through effective and creative strategies. Marketers choose marketing mix (4P), management strategies and other strategies to achieve the plan's goals and then draw up an implementation plan. The company also checks to ensure the right marketing organization is in place of execution (staff, departmental structure, application service providers, etc. outside the company).

5. *Actions (Implementation)*. This action is a real act of tactics that we have planned. It is in this action that the implementation of the planning.

6. *Control*. At this point we will monitor what we have done to our plans. In this section there will also be evaluating if there are things that are not appropriate.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Digital Marketing Strategies in SOSTAC Analysis

In this subchapter section penileti will describe the results of the research that has been done and associate it with the theory used. The results are then associated with relevant theories to answer the research focus that has been determined in the previous chapter. Based on the results of researchers' interviews with Grandma's House *Coffeeshop* marketing team about digital *marketing* strategies using Instagram media in increasing *brand awareness*, researchers get interview data that can help answer the research that is being done. Berjoins the researchers will describe the results of the research that has been done. The use of SOSTAC's marketing communication strategy in executing Grandma's House's *Coffeeshop* strategy on Instagram media.

1. Situation

Based on the results of research and interviews with grandma's house *coffeeshop* marketing team explained that many similar businesses in the form of coffee shops are found, especially in bintaro area, South Jakarta. In terms of advantages, Grandma's House *coffeeshop* has a signature or main menu owned with homemade concoctions that can not be found in other coffee shops, although the main ingredient used is coffee, but does not limit innovation from the Team and especially baristas who "play around" to detect more signatures that will increase over time. Finished doing this new innovation, they always update posts on social media Instagram as a promotional platform and also to get closer to *followers* and prospective consumers. *Coffeeshop* Grandma's House also always provides the best service for every consumer who comes in polite language and seems *friendly* so that consumers feel comfortable and close in accordance with Grandma's House's slogan of "as comfortable as grandma's house". Not only that, Grandma's House also provides *public space* for the needs of consumers who want to do *meetings* or just get together with family, of course with a capacity and price that is quite worth *it* for renting a place that is very rarely found especially in coffee shops such as Grandma's House. The disadvantage of Grandma's House *coffeeshop* is the many competitors of MSMEs with similar coffee shop businesses located in bintaro numbers, and also still in the process of opening new branches in other cities that require discussion and a long time. In terms of opportunities, Grandma's House *coffeeshop* several times held major events such as one of the latest of the humanitarian collaboration event with Rapid Response Action (ACT), between the organization of the International Relations Student Association (Himahi) budi Luhur University and became the sponsor of the venue for the inauguration of jabatan one of the taekwondo clubs in Indonesia. For the threat in Grandma's House is the growth rate of coffee shops that sell similar coffee products or the addition of *signatures* that are characteristic of the menu that becomes a mainstay in the coffee shop itself. Of course this is all related to the theory used by researchers that all organizations have strengths and weaknesses on the business side. This is related to SWOT analysis that each company has its own strategy in achieving this determination and weakness when combined with opportunities or threats that will be a reference for an effort to set goals and strategies.

2. Objectives

Based on the results of interviews conducted with the team from Grandma's House coffee shop, that they have successfully implemented some of its vision and mission such as introducing products, but Grandma's House continues to conduct research such as so that the products it sells can make consumers satisfied both in terms of taste, price, and friendly service. Looking at the price and taste that can be said to be quite *worth it*, of course Grandma's House expects the products they sell can be enjoyed and give confidence to consumers.

3. Strategic Planning

How when we can achieve the goal, will be explained specifically in the planning of this strategy, such as sales promotions carried out. Based on the results of research and interviews with the Grandma's House team, social media now certainly facilitates their sales promotion. Things that are done such as posting activities on social media Instagram @grandmahousee either through the Instagram *Story* feature or the latest post updates in the form of *feeds* that contain activities that are there. Also in terms of activities such as *live music* at every weekend that is done to attract consumers to enjoy their coffee while enjoying entertaining music, as well as *offline* and *online* promos that consumers can get when buying their products by going directly to the store or interesting promos through the Gojek or Grab applications.

4. Tactics

Tactics are detailed explanations of the steps that will be taken to the implementation of a strategy. Based on the results of research and interviews conducted with the Grandma's House team, planning ideas is already in place and is run starting from always making innovations or creating *the* latest signature variants combined with *flavors* that are *in* among coffee lovers. The design of this idea is certainly to create the *image* of Grandma's House as a coffee shop that is always evolving with new flavors and does not stop at that product – that's all.

5. Action

Action is a concrete act of pre-planned tactics. Based on the results of research and interviews with the Grandma's House team, one of the internal activities in the form of meetings or *meetings* conducted is divided into several sessions such as monthly meetings and meetings when going to carry out or become a sponsor at an event. One of the keys to the importance of taking action, ensures that all parties involved in the meeting must convey input or criticism because they think through it can be born a new ideas.

6. Controlling

At this point we will monitor and find out whether the strategies and tactics on the main target are appropriate or not and in this section there will also be *evaluating* if there is a section that is not appropriate. Based on the results of research and interviews conducted with the Grandma's House team, existing strategies are dynamic, some are arguably appropriate and not appropriate depending on the conditions in the field, but Grandma's House does not rule out the possibility of changing the prevailing strategy.

B. Instagram Social Media Digital Marketing Strategy

According to Drury Veby Zilfania, (2014: 17) mentions that the use of *social media* has begun to be often used in marketing, communication, 1045offices or departments that deal directly with consumers or stakeholders. In business also *social media* is one of the channels that support communication in marketing merchandise quickly and profitably compared to selling directly to the market. The merger of social media with marketing is to support marketing performance as technology and information evolve.

Coffeeshop or Grandma's House coffee shop as one of the businesses in the field of coffee in doing marketing communication is done by applying several ways. Based on the results of research and interviews conducted with grandma's house team about *digital marketing*, namely the utilization of Instagram social media whose users almost reached 79% as a profitable marketing tool. Grandma's House store explained also in its use more *updates* so indirectly much profitable through social media.

Grandma's House's social media is Instagram, and this coffee shop has been actively using it as a means of promotion since 2020, with the aim of introducing products sold to the wider community that not only cover the Bintaro area but spread to other regions. The advantages of Instagram social media that Grandma's House uses can not be separated from the visual appearance is considered more attractive tobring consumers to konversi compared to otherways. In posting photos, Grandma's House Instagram account always uses photos of their own shots so that prospective consumers know the appearance of the products sold.

Fig 2 Coffee posts on Grandma's House with interesting visuals

Fig 3 Caption in the post

C. Instagram feed

Grandma's House team itself explains the advantages of Instagram in addition to posting videos or images, in terms of *captions* can also attract the attention of consumers when reading it with sentences that are easy to understand and read for their *followers*.

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of research on Grandma's House's *digital marketing strategy* in increasing *brand awareness* through Instagram social media is by determining the social media that will be usedand planningstrategies. Instagram is one of the social media chosen by Grandma's House to promote and build awareness of coffee shop brands in the hearts of consumers. The activity carried out is in the form of making posts and captions that are processed in such a way as to attract potential consumers. This posting activity becomes one of the important things in marketing communication that can reach consumers widely and can disseminate information widely and widely about products from a business industry / MSME. Grandma's House also uses Instagram social media as its promotional medium because it is considered effective, dynamic and has unlimited reach. By presenting posts generated from their own shots so that consumers know what products are sold and generate high interest to buy one of the products they sell. Using the slogan "As comfortable as grandma's house" became one of Grandma's House's strategies in introducing a coffee shop that is comfortable equipped with a *signature* served asone coffee shop that is able to compete with other coffee shops in theBintaro area.

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